

DESIGN AND TEST ON THE NONLINEAR PE-EM HYBRID ENERGY HARVESTING STRUCTURE

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Keywords: Design and Test, Nonlinear, Hybrid, Piezoelectric-electromagnetic, Energy Harvester.

ABSTRACT

At present, the study of environmental vibration energy harvesting mainly concentrated in the hybrid energy harvester. In this paper, a nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvesting structure is designed, and the nonlinear magnetic force is introduced in the hybrid structure to change the resonant frequency and the bandwidth of the harvester. The theoretical model of nonlinear hybrid harvester system is established. The experimental results of the nonlinear hybrid harvester show that the direction and size of the magnetic force have great influence on the performance of the nonlinear hybrid harvester and also show that the bandwidth of harvester is improved and the working frequency of harvester can be adjusted with the appearance of nonlinear magnetic force. And the designed nonlinear hybrid harvester has good environmental adaptability because the bandwidth increases.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with the increasing application of wireless sensor network (WSN) in environmental monitoring and forecasting, health care, intelligent home, city intelligent transportation. Long term stable power supply for wireless sensors has been an important problem in the development of WSN^[1-5]. According to the application characteristics of wireless sensors, harvesting energy from ambient environment vibration becomes an ideal power supply mode^[6-9]. There are many ways to convert ambient energy into electrical energy, such as photocells, thermocouples, vibration, and wind and so on. Among these energy converting ways, the ambient vibration energy harvesting is more attractive because the vibration is everywhere in our daily environment. So it has broad application to convert energy directly from the ambient vibration

At present, the study of environmental vibration energy harvesting mainly concentrated in the hybrid energy harvester^[10-12]. At the same time, in order to enhance the environmental adaptability of ambient vibration harvester, more and more researchers have focused on nonlinear hybrid harvester. Mann and Foaisal designed a nonlinear magnetic spring harvester. The harvesting bandwidth can be optimized through changing the size of the magnet and the magnet distance. Challa V R, Owens Jiang W A, Li P et al are also studied on the nonlinear hybrid harvester^[13-18].

2 DESIGN OF NONLINEAR PE-EM HYBRID ENERGY HARVESTER

The designed nonlinear piezoelectric-electromagnetic PE-EM hybrid harvesting structure is shown in figure 1. The nonlinear magnetic force is introduced in the hybrid structure to change the resonant frequency and the bandwidth of the harvester^[19-23].

Figure 1 Schematic of nonlinear (PE-EM) hybrid harvesting structure

The movable magnet as mass is supported by double-clamped compound beam, and two coils are placed above and below the movable magnet respectively, two magnets are put in the coils. In addition, piezoelectric layers polarized in the beam thickness direction are died on the top surface of beams. Based on piezoelectric effect and law of electromagnetic induction, PZT layers and coils will output energy under the external vibration excitation. The magnetic force between the upper and lower magnet and the movable magnet causes the structural vibration to be nonlinear.

3 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF NONLINEAR PE-EM HYBRID ENERGY HARVESTER

According to the literature^[24-26], the magnetic force between the two cylindrical magnets is

$$F_m = \frac{3\mu_0 M_1 V_1 \cdot M_0 V_0}{2\pi d^4} \quad (1)$$

Where $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m is magnetic permeability, V_1 and V_0 are magnet volume respectively, M_1 and M_0 are magnetization respectively, d is static distance between two magnets. In the design of nonlinear hybrid harvester, if the static distance of upper and lower magnets, the force between two magnets is

$$F_m(z) = k_1 z + k_3 z^3 \quad (2)$$

where

$$k_1 = -12\mu_0 M_1 V_1 \frac{M_0 V_0}{\pi d^5} \quad (3)$$

$$k_3 = \frac{5}{d^2} k_1 \quad (4)$$

According to figure 1, the designed nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvesting structure can be equivalent

to a mass-spring-damping vibration system with nonlinear stiffness. So, the state equation of nonlinear hybrid harvester can be expressed as

$$m_e \ddot{z}(t) + c_m \dot{z}(t) + k(z(t) - z_e(t)) = F_e(t) - g_e V_p(t) - \theta I_{em}(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{V_p(t)}{R_p} + C_p \dot{V}_p(t) - \theta \dot{z}(t) = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$L_c \dot{I}_{em}(t) + (R_c + R_m) I_{em}(t) - g_e \dot{z}(t) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Where $\ddot{z}(t)$ is excitation acceleration, m_e is equivalent mass of vibration system, c_m and k are damping coefficient and linear stiffness of the vibration system respectively. R_p is external load of piezoelectric element, C_p is equivalent capacitance of piezoelectric layer, V_p output voltage of piezoelectric element, I_{em} is output current of electromagnetic element, R_c is coil resistance, L_c is coil inductance, R_m is external load of electromagnetic element, θ and g_e are piezoelectric and electromagnetic transfer factor respectively.

In the low frequency vibration, the coil impedance is mainly considered as the coil resistance, and the inductance of the coil can be neglected when the nonlinear energy harvesting device is excited by harmonic excitation. When the excitation acceleration of the harvester is $\ddot{z}(t) = -Y \cos(\omega t + \phi)$, and let $\omega_n^2 = \frac{K}{m_e}$, $K = k + k_1$, $2\zeta\omega_n = \frac{c_m}{m_e}$, $\beta = \frac{g_e}{R_c + R_m}$, $\mu = \frac{1}{R_p C_p}$. According to the harmonic balance method and considering small nonlinearity and the response of the energy harvesting system is mainly single harmonic frequency, the vibration response and the output voltage of piezoelectric element and output current of electromagnetic element can be expressed as

$$z(t) = A_1 \cos \omega t \quad (8)$$

$$V_p(t) = A_2 \cos(\omega t + \phi_1) \quad (9)$$

$$I_{em}(t) = A_3 \cos(\omega t + \phi_2) \quad (10)$$

The equation(8)~(10) are substituted into equation (5) and the higher order harmonic terms is neglected, the equation (5) can be expressed as

$$A_1(\omega_n^2 - \omega^2) \cos \omega t - 2A_1\zeta\omega_n\omega \sin \omega t + \frac{3k_3 A_1^3}{4m_e} \cos \omega t + \frac{A_2\theta}{m_e} \cos(\omega t + \phi_1) + \frac{A_3 g_e}{m_e} \cos(\omega t + \phi_2) = Y \cos(\omega t + \phi) \quad (11)$$

If the coefficients of $\sin \omega t$ and $\cos \omega t$ on both sides of the equation (11) are equal,

$$A_1(\omega_n^2 - \omega^2) + A_1^3 \frac{3k_3}{4m_e} + A_2 \frac{\theta}{m_e} \cos \phi_1 + A_3 \frac{g_e}{m_e} \cos \phi_2 = Y \cos \phi \quad (12)$$

$$2A_1\zeta\omega_n\omega + A_2\frac{\theta}{m_e}\sin\phi_1 + A_3\frac{g_e}{m_e}\sin\phi_2 = Y\sin\varphi \quad (13)$$

Where $A_2, A_3, \cos\phi_1$ and $\cos\phi_2$ can be obtained from the following analysis.

The equation(8)~(10) are substituted into equation (6), then

$$-A_2\omega\sin(\omega t + \phi_1) + \mu A_2\cos(\omega t + \phi_1) + \frac{\theta}{C_p}A_1\omega\sin\omega t = 0 \quad (14)$$

If the coefficients of $\sin\omega t$ and $\cos\omega t$ on both sides of the equation (14) are equal,

$$-A_2\omega\cos\phi_1 - \mu A_2\sin\phi_1 + \frac{\theta}{C_p}A_1\omega = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$-A_2\omega\sin\phi_1 + \mu A_2\cos\phi_1 = 0 \quad (16)$$

And

$$\sin\phi_1 = \frac{\mu}{\omega}\cos\phi_1 \quad (17)$$

$$\cos\phi_1 = \frac{\theta\omega^2}{C_p(\omega^2 + \mu^2)}\frac{A_1}{A_2} \quad (18)$$

The equation (17) and equation (18) are added after the square, then

$$A_2 = \frac{\theta\omega}{C_p\sqrt{\omega^2 + \mu^2}}A_1 \quad (19)$$

Using the same method, the equation(8)~(10) are substituted into equation (7), then

$$\cos\phi_2 = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$\sin\phi_2 = \frac{A_1}{A_3}\beta\omega \quad (21)$$

$$A_3 = A_1\beta\omega \quad (22)$$

Substituting the equation (19) and (22) into equation(12) and (13),

$$A_1(\omega_n^2 - \omega^2) + A_1^3\frac{3k_3}{4m_e} + A_1\frac{\theta}{m_e}\frac{\theta\omega^2}{C_p(\omega^2 + \mu^2)} = Y\cos\varphi \quad (23)$$

$$2A_1\zeta\omega_n\omega + A_1\frac{\theta}{m_e}\frac{\mu\theta\omega}{C_p(\omega^2 + \mu^2)} + A_1\frac{g_e}{m_e}\beta\omega = Y\sin\varphi \quad (24)$$

The equation (23) and equation (24) are added after the square, then the amplitude of the mass block is obtained

$$z_M^2 = A_1^2 = \frac{Y^2}{[(\omega_n^2 - \omega^2) + z_M^2 \frac{3k_3}{4m_e} + \frac{\theta}{m_e} \frac{\theta\omega^2}{C_p(\omega^2 + \mu^2)}]^2 + [2\zeta\omega_n\omega + \frac{\theta}{m_e} \frac{\mu\theta\omega}{C_p(\omega^2 + \mu^2)} + \frac{g_e}{m_e} \beta\omega]^2} \quad (25)$$

So, the average output power of piezoelectric and electromagnetic energy harvesting element are expressed as

$$P_p = \frac{1}{2} \frac{V_p^2}{R_p} = \frac{\theta^2 \omega^2}{2R_p C_p^2 [\omega^2 + (\frac{1}{R_p C_p})^2]} z_M^2 \quad (26)$$

$$P_{em} = \frac{1}{2} R_m I_{em}^2 = \frac{R_m g_e^2 \omega^2}{2(R_c + R_m)^2} z_M^2 \quad (27)$$

And the total output average power of the designed nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester is

$$P = P_p + P_{em} = \left\{ \frac{\theta^2 \omega^2}{2R_p C_p [\omega^2 + (\frac{1}{R_p C_p})^2]} + \frac{g_e^2 \omega^2}{2R_m (R_c + R_m)^2} \right\} z_M^2 \quad (28)$$

4 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON NONLINEAR PE-EM HYBRID HARVESTER

The schematic of experimental system for designed nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester is shown in figure 2. For the sake to test output characteristics of nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester, the nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester is fabricated. The whole setup of the device is mounted on the vibrating shaker which is connected to a signal generator through a power amplifier. The signal generator is used to provide the source vibration frequency and amplitude excitation. An accelerometer is used to record vibration acceleration, high-speed camera is used to record the vibration of magnet and the displacement of magnet will be analyzed through the video analysis software and dynamic signal analyzer is used to record output voltage of piezoelectric and electromagnetic element. In order to accurately compare harvesting performance of different energy harvesting structures. The size parameters of double-clamped compound beam, mass block and PZT layer of PE element are the same as that of hybrid harvester. And the distance between the fixed magnet and moveable magnet can be adjusted by the screw thread on the screw rod.

Figure 2. Schematic of test system for nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester

Figure 3 The comparison between the output of linear and nonlinear harvester

4.1 Performance comparison of linear and nonlinear energy harvester

During the test, the harmonic excitation is 0.6g, the comparison between the output of linear and nonlinear energy harvester is shown in figure 3.

The experimental results show that when the force between two magnets is magnetic attraction, the working frequency of nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester can be reduced to 39.3Hz, the 3dB bandwidth is increased to 7.5Hz. This effectively overcomes the defects of linear harvester with high resonance frequency and narrow working bandwidth. When the force between two magnets is magnetic repulsion, the working frequency of nonlinear PE-EM hybrid harvester is 126Hz, 3dB bandwidth is 4.5Hz. Seeing from figure 3, the output power of the nonlinear hybrid harvester is higher when the action force between magnets is repulsion.

4.2 Performance test of nonlinear hybrid harvester with repulsion

The harmonic excitation is still keep 0.6g. The output performance of the nonlinear hybrid harvester is tested when magnet distance is 2.5mm, 3mm and 4mm respectively on the condition that the force between two magnets is repulsion.

Figure 4 is the relationship between the output voltage and the excitation frequency of the piezoelectric element when the force between two magnets is repulsion. And figure 5 is the relationship between the output power and the excitation frequency of the piezoelectric element when the force between two magnets is repulsion.

Figure 4 The V-F of piezoelectric element

Figure 5 The P-F of piezoelectric element

Seeing from figure 4 and figure 5, with the decrease of the magnet distance, the nonlinear repulsion increases, the resonant frequency of the system increases, the magnet amplitude decreases, the working bandwidth of nonlinear harvester increases, and the output power under the optimal load becomes small.

Figure 6 is the relationship between the output voltage and the excitation frequency of the electromagnetic element when the force between two magnets is repulsion. And figure 7 is the relationship between the output power and the excitation frequency of the electromagnetic element when the force between two magnets is repulsion.

Figure 6 the V-F of electromagnetic element

Figure 7 the P-F of electromagnetic element

The changes of electromagnetic element output voltage and output power with the distance change when the magnetic force is repulsion are not obvious. Seeing from figure 6 and figure 7, the output power and output voltage of electromagnetic element are maximum when the distance is 4mm.

Under the nonlinear magnetic repulsion, the relationship between the total output power of nonlinear hybrid harvester and the excitation frequency at different distances is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8 the relationship between total output power and excitation frequency

Seeing from figure 8, the total output power of nonlinear hybrid harvester has maximum value when the distance is 4mm and has minimum value when the distance is 3mm. Therefore, the total

output of the nonlinear hybrid harvester is mainly determined by the performance of electromagnetic element.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The designed hybrid harvester has nonlinearity due to the introduction of magnet force between magnets. The theoretical model of nonlinear hybrid harvester system is established. And the bandwidth of harvester increases because the action of magnetic force. Especially for the output power of nonlinear hybrid harvester is slightly higher than that of linear harvester when the magnetic force is repulsion. The experimental results of the nonlinear hybrid harvester show that the direction and size of the magnetic force have great influence on the performance of the nonlinear hybrid harvester and also show that the bandwidth of harvester is improved and the working frequency of harvester can be adjusted with the appearance of nonlinear magnetic force. The working bandwidth, output power, output voltage and optimum load of nonlinear hybrid harvester can be influenced by the magnetic force. So, the designed nonlinear hybrid harvester has good environmental adaptability because the bandwidth increases. In the design of nonlinear hybrid energy harvesting structure, we should choose the appropriate nonlinear force according to the working environment.

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